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VALUE ORIENTATIONS AND ATTITUDES: SPECIFIC OF MANIFESTATION AND RELATIONSHIP AT ADOLESCENCE AND YOUTH AGES

Study of value orientations and attitudes comprises an analysis of the scientific approaches of various theories in the field of philosophy, psychology, pedagogy regarding the definitions of the concepts: value, value orientation, attitudes. There are highlighted various scientific positions regarding attitudes in relationship with other elements of personality, the structural components of value orientation, the process of their formation and functioning.

The purpose of research. *Determination of manifestation and relationship particularities of value orientations and attitudes at adolescence and youth ages.*

Methodology. *The following tools were used in the experiment to diagnose attitudes – «Attitudes most frequently adopted» by Fabrice Lacombe and value orientation – the technique of identifying the value orientations.*

Novelty of research. *The data obtained permitted to determine relationship of attitudes and values from structural content perspective; to establish the specific of manifestation and relationship between values and attitudes from structural perspective of their functioning, particularities of their manifestations and relationship at contemporary adolescents and youths.*

Conclusions. *The study realized from theoretical and experimental perspectives allowed: to highlight the process of values shaping focused on attitudes formation and the reverse of functioning, manifestation of attitudes subordinated to personality's value system; to establish the specificity of manifestation and correlation of values and attitudes at contemporary adolescents and youths. The coherent and structured formation of attitudes through the organization and development of behaviors, cognition, affective sphere, convictions, and consequently the values shaping of the subject involved in the educational process will ensure the progressive evolution of the personality development beginning from adolescence and youth ages.*

Keywords: *value orientation, value, attitude, adolescence, youth.*

Introduction. In various sources of information, in daily life we have accustomed to visualizing, hearing and using such notions as «value», «value orientation», «attitude» that have already become part of our whole life. However, for most people it is difficult to explain, to define these concepts, to establish tangential aspects between them, but in an attempt to interpret, it is called a concrete value or it describes the state, the position of the subject in its affective or cognitive perspective.

Theoretical review. The concept of 'value orientation' has a close connection with the concept of value which can be explained from the structuralist perspective and from the position of functionality. In order to understand the complexity of the concept 'value' it is useful to examine the scientific positions from the point of view of the various fields.

The concept of 'value orientation' has a close connection with the concept of value which can be explained from the structuralist perspective and from the position of functionality. In order to understand the complexity of the concept 'value' it is useful to examine the scientific positions from the point of view of the various fields.

A. Petre affirming the fundamentality of the notion of value for philosophy discovers its educational essence, because philosophy not only explains the world through logical values, but transforms it, in accordance with human ethical ideals. The value, according to the same author, «is neither an attribute of the subject nor of the object, but a functional relation of both ... in the phenomenon of value we have two constituent elements: the subject and the object. The subject of value is the person, and the object is the thing. Value is the result of a process of knowledge. By culture itself we must understand the realization of all values ... Culture is an objectification of the human spirit in activity, in works» [1].

Examining the multiple conceptual approaches with regard to values we find the rallying to culture, correspondingly the interest given to the definition given to the notion of culture by T.Vianu being more complete and far from being exhaustive, it is limited to the human activity of value creation. T.Vianu inscribes pedagogy in the axiology of culture due to the fact that it constitutes that domain of human activity which is essentially a domain of creating human values. Viewed from this angle, culture is an axiology of education, because the student (the educated) does not only acquire values created by mankind, but, by appropriating them, he creates his own knowledge, capacities, attitudes, which, on the one hand, they they are values themselves, and on the other hand, they are the potential mechanisms for creating new objectified values in science, literature, art, etc. [5].

From a psychological perspective, values are the subjective product of a person, his/her psychological states, feelings, emotions or volition and represents the relationship between a verifying consciousness and an object, a relationship in which the subject objects his/her psychological predispositions to value. Any representation or impression is related to feelings of pleasure / displeasure, approval / disapproval, soul states that impose themselves as feelings accompanying values.

A. Meeinong stresses the absolute role of feeling in determining value but, not every feeling constitutes the condition of the genesis of value, but only that through which one attends to objects, «one thing has value when it satisfies our need» [as cited in 1].

G. Schmöller and the representative of contemporary pragmatism, R. Perry, identify value with utility, with something that satisfies human interests: «what is good for life appears as value, what is harmful, is worthless» [as cited in 1].

The representatives of logical empiricism (A.J. Ayer, B. Russell, etc.) distinguish the values from tastes, preferences, desires and do not attribute them to the objective truth. B. Russell in the work «Human knowledge and its limits» approaches the validations of the cognitive-affective sphere of personality, pointing to the problem of axiology outside the field of knowledge: «When we say that something has value we do not seek an independent fact of personal feelings, but give expression to our own emotions ... Those who speak of the objective nature of value, are confused because the desire is particular, whereas what we want is universal» [as cited in 6].

Representatives of the existentialist current (R. Richter, J. Köhler, W. Wundt, L. Lavelle etc.) deduce the value from the human volition; the psychological condition that generates values is the contribution of the respective value bearer to human happiness. What is desired and becomes value.

In W. Wundt's vision, exposed in the work «Logic and Ethics», the source of value is only volition in the initial stage of its psychological development; it reveals three characteristics: value determination, goal setting, and life affirmation. If according to R. Richter the value is confused with the purpose, with all that is desired, N. Hartman goes further, conditioning the quality of the value to the quality of purpose [as cited in 1].

V. Sopov and L. Karpushina define the notion of value as an attitude of the subject towards various facts, events of life, the object and the subject and their recognition as being important in life. The authors analyze the following values and spheres of life: self-development; spiritual satisfaction; creativity; social contacts; personal prestige; the high material situation; skills; personal level of individuality; the sphere of professional life; the sphere of studies, education; the sphere of family life; the sphere of social life; the sphere of fun; the sphere of physical activity [8, 61-66].

Personal values represent one of the most important subsystems of the sphere of personality content. Based on the classification of the psychological nature of the individual values proposed by D. Leontiev, the authors L. Karpushina and A. Kaptsov assume that personal values have a double essence. On the one hand, this implies the relationship (the relationship, the attitude) that has the function of directing and structuring, on the

other hand the values are located in the same line with the needs and reasons, presenting in themselves the value education, which shows power of stimulation, that is they have orientation and motivation function [9].

T. Parsons defined values as the ultimate motive of the actions of individuals and communities, as defining elements for social life. From here, the way to identify their manifestations results, both through behaviors, and especially through attitudes, the latter being the direct expression of values [as cited in 4].

For M. Rokeach the values are similar to the attitudes. But attitudes are more elementary and values are deeper, determining attitudes [as cited in 2]. This is the generally accepted viewpoint in sociology today. The distinction between the two concepts becomes clearer if we note that the attitudes refer rather to specific objects and situations, while the values represent orientations associated with more general classes of objects and situations.

B. Voicu mentions the fact that, from a psychological perspective, values represent elements of orientation of individuals in the surrounding world [7]. They present decoding of the possible actions that allow the identification of potential gratifications, benefits derived from the scales of each one's preferences, depending on their personal motivations, needs and aspirations.

Value orientations and values are of major importance in the personality system having an impact on our life, penetrating in all layers: social, economic, political, etc.

Cl. Kluckhohn defines value orientation as an «organized and generalized conception, influencing the behavior, with respect to nature, the place of man in it, to human relations with others and to the desirable and undesirable, as they may be related to the environment. and inter-human relations». As an example of the value orientation can serve religiosity, as a value in the given example is the religious ritual, which manifests itself through attitudes towards going to church, prayers, fasting, etc. [as cited in 7].

D. Antoci defines *value orientation* as a process of monitoring by a value or by set of values of the assembly of beliefs, attitudes, behaviors that are in hierarchical interrelation within the personality system. Whole unitary that combines correlation of hierarchically placed values according to the preferences and current situations of personality constitutes a *system of values*, which is in continuously static changing for a certain period (relatively short) of subject's life and dynamic development over a longer period of life with reaching the points of transcendence.

P. Andrei mentions that the fourth fundamental property of values concerns the knowledge of values through the analysis of their manifestations, either attitudes, beliefs or behaviors [1].

Attitudes, unlike knowledge and capacities, are less understood and less followed in educational action, although they are just the main acquisitions of educators. The attitudes constitute significant relations of the human being towards the phenomena of the world outside of it and towards the phenomena of its intimate universe. Pedagogically, the student's attitudes encompass his knowledge and abilities.

Attitudes can be evaluated if their concrete manifestations are known. These are: in the emotional sphere: emotions, feelings, soul states (including literary characters); in desirable sphere: desires, aspirations, ideals; in the volitional sphere: acts of will; in the field of evaluation: opinions, assessments / self-assessments, evaluative acts; in the conceptual sphere: beliefs, ideas, principles, personal concepts, etc.

A special sphere of attitudes manifestation is the behavioral one, in which the first five types of attitudes manifestations occur, but it does not represent a sum of them, the human behaviors having their own particular value as attitudes.

A. Chircev analyzing the scientific positions in the field of psychology regarding the interpretation of attitudes found that they are characterized by elaborating definitions appropriate to the notion 'attitude', by identifying structural variables that condition them and trying to transpose the attitudes through the schemes established for their classification [3].

A. Chircev highlights some definitions of the scholars with regard to attitude. E.g:

Cantril after G. Allport: an attitude is a more or less permanent state of readiness / readiness of a mental organization, which predisposes an individual to react in a characteristic way to an object and situation with which he is in relation [as cited in 3, 24-25];

Bernard: an attitude is a process of adapting behavior, essentially incomplete or potential. It is a disposition of the organism towards the object or a situation ... when adaptation is made, the attitude disappears being retained in memory or in the habitual disposition of the organism [as cited in 3, 24-25].

Fulfilling an analysis of the multiple definitions of the notion of attitude, A. Chircev [3, 22-25] concludes that to itself is assigned an adaptive postural organization, a neuromuscular disposition, a process of mental preparation for action and a complex of emotional experiences.

The indispensable factor in the initial formation of attitudes is that of socialization, which takes place in the socio-cultural-historical environment within the educational process. The attitudes formed have a relatively defined object / subject / situation / reference phenomenon and of a conceptual or empirical nature. The relatively definitive determination and the change of attitude occurs through the accumulation of experiences and the continuous interrelation with reference objects. It is very important to realise that everybody of us is a product of our environment, environment where we grown up, studied and were educated. Our environment directly or indirectly influence our thoughts, actions, and behaviours. The choice of environment is possible from a certain period, when we understand and realize that the environment promotes our development and directs us towards success.

Thus, the attitude constitutes a relatively determined and contoured internal position from the affective and cognitive perspective within the socialization process in the socio-cultural-historical environment through education, personal

experience with the object / subject / situation / phenomenon that was in direct interrelation process. with the person concerned and manifested / expressed through various ways of outsourcing.

Experimental research design. *The purpose of research:* determination of manifestation and relationship particularities of value orientations and attitudes at adolescence and youth ages.

Methodology: the following tools were used in the experiment to diagnose attitudes – «Attitudes most frequently adopted» by Fabrice Lacombe, and value orientations – the technique of identifying the value orientations.

The research was undertaken in April-May, 2019, in frame of general and higher education institutions at the north, central, and south part of the Republic of Moldova. In the investigation 374 adolescents and young people between the ages of 14/15-18/19 and 20-35 years were involved.

Results and discussions. In order to achieve the purpose of the research, one of the objectives was to study the attitudes of adolescent subjects and young people. Applying the diagnostic tool to Fabrice Lacombe allows us to analyze how the subjects are interrelated. The data obtained are the result of the self-evaluation of the subject's own position towards something, the mode of action based on the evaluation of the proposed statements from 0 to 3 points. The results obtained describe the internal state of the subjects, which requires a multidimensional analysis with possible subsequent intervention. Figure 1 shows the average indices of the attitudes of adolescents obtained from the application of Lacombe's instrument.

Figure 1. Average indices of adolescents' attitudes according to «Attitudes most frequently adopted» by Fabrice Lacombe (points)

Data analysis illustrates the quality of the way subjects are positioned from the perspective of six relational trends. The highest indices are found in the attitude of openness which is calculated on the basis of two types of openness: dominant and reserve. The attitude of dominant opening (with the highest index of 16.79 p.) is characterized by free, uncontrolled exposure, safe manifestation, determined relatively definitively by the subject through accumulated knowledge and experiences. At the same time, the indication of the attitude of the reserve opening is not much lower, the difference constitutes 0,10 points (16.66 p.), Which means that the subjects also have some unclear, reservations in order to expose some reactions to those that happened from the outside, the fact it can be explained by the lack of knowledge or the presence of counter-experiences, which require clarification, awareness, characteristic of the adolescent age. Correspondingly, the average opening attitude is equal with 16.73 p., that can be described by asserting one's self, empathy, understanding of the other, trust, functional clarity.

Index of 15.26 p. placed at the lower limit of the average level refers to the manipulation attitude that is characterized by diminishing the distraction of attention, confusion, pursuit of a hidden objective.

Figure 2 shows the results of young people's attitudinal tendencies.

After examining the data of the young people, we distinguish some indices that stand out on the background of others. The highest result (16.87 p.), as in the case of adolescent subjects, is noticeable in the average attitude of openness, which is characterized by the free way of relating, communicability, although some moments remain to be materialized, clarified in order to determine clear and stable attitude. Compared with the attitudinal tendencies manifested we highlight the aggressive submission (16.47 p.) which can be described by withdrawing itself into a passive opposition, cynicism, laughter, which demonstrates the subject's opposition to the situation or reality, which indicates on the gradual contouring. of the internal position of young people. Some of the lowest results are highlighted by passive submission (13.9 p.) which less manifests itself through withdrawal itself, acceptance without discernment, passive flight.

Another objective of the research was the study of the value orientations of adolescents and young people. For this we applied the technique of identifying the value orientations. The obtained results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Average indices of young people's attitudes according to «Attitudes most frequently adopted» by Fabrice Lacombe (points)

Figure 3. Average indices of value orientations of adolescents and young people according to Identification of Value Orientation Instrument (points)

Examining presented indices gives us opportunity to highlight the first place of such value orientations as achievement / fulfillment (0.87 p. – for teenagers and 0.88 – for young people) and family happiness (0.83 p. – for teenagers; 0.88 p. – in young people) who are almost identical at both ages of the subjects of the experimental group. Comparative analysis of the data shows the change of the indices to the health variable from 0.76 p. in adolescence with growth up to 0.93 p. in young people, which means that with the age, the meaning of health becomes more and more current. Changes to growth from adolescence to youth are observed with respect from 0.75 p. at 0.81 p. At the same time, the learning variable changes from 0.70 p. to 0.78 p. which confirms the gradual recovery of the studies during the maturation. The desire to be independent is becoming stronger towards the young and, correspondingly, the autonomy increases from 0.69 p. up to 0.74 p. During the maturation the researched subjects increasingly value the financial security and at the young age it constitutes 0,77 p. (increasing from 0.69 p.).

Following comparative analysis of the data, we observe the variables which values are diminished towards youth: friendship (0.75 p.), Balance (0.71 p.), Teamwork (0.63 p.), Leadership (0.56 p.), entrepreneurship (0.48 p.).

To determine the particularities of the relation of the value orientation and the attitudes we determined the Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

Pearson statistical test through SPSS program application allowed us to determine the following correlations between values and attitudes presented in table 1.

Table 1

Pearson correlation coefficients (r) between value orientations and attitudes of adolescents and youths

<i>Attitudes</i> <i>Values</i>	<i>Dominant opening</i>	<i>Rezerve opening</i>	<i>Opening media</i>	<i>Aggressivity</i>	<i>Manipulation</i>	<i>Passive submission</i>	<i>Active submission</i>	<i>Aggressive submission</i>
Balance	-0,121	-,230, p=0,000	-,203, p=0,001	-0,076	-0,103	0,019	-,123, p=0,049	-0,091
Creation	-0,061	-,128, p=0,041	-0,11	-,134, p=0,032	-,185, 0,003	-0,043	-0,069	-0,083
Competitive ness	-,132, p=0,035	-,141, p=0,024	-,156, p=0,012	-0,057	-0,122	-,145, p=0,020	-0,08	-,131, p=0,035
Charity	-,185, p=0,003	0,021	-0,089	-0,055	-0,029	-0,044	-0,076	-0,054
Entrepreneur ship	-0,051	-0,103	-0,089	-0,037	-,147, p=0,019	-0,093	-,154, p=0,013	-0,078
Fame	-0,08	-,136, p=0,030	-,125, p=0,046	-0,115	-,143, p=0,22	-,132, p=0,034	-,146, p=0,019	-,154, p=0,014
Learning	-,146, p=0,019	-0,1	-,140, p=0,025	-,147, p=0,018	-0,121	-0,03	-0,103	-,151, p=0,016
Free time	0,004	-,129, p=0,039	-0,074	-0,017	-0,048	0,055	-0,032	-0,046
Personal improvement	-0,051	-,134, p=0,032	-0,107	-,154, p=0,013	-,186, p=0,003	-,155, p=0,013	-0,085	-0,095
Safety	-0,015	-,136, p=0,029	-0,089	-0,074	-0,028	-0,041	-0,115	-0,112
Protection	-,128, p=0,040	-0,069	-0,111	-,161, p=0,010	-0,119	-,131, p=0,013	-,213, p=0,001	-,168, p=0,007
Self-expression	-,174, p=0,005	-,144, p=0,021	-,181, p=0,004	-,131, p=0,036	-0,082	-0,099	-,169, p=0,007	-0,095
Status	-0,075	-,148, p=0,017	-,130, p=0,038	-0,086	-0,054	-0,091	-0,061	-0,02

According to correlation coefficients, we find the dominant presence of the significant negative relationship of medium and high intensity. The negative ratio is established between creation: reserve opening ($r = -0,128, p \leq 0,041$), which means that any creativity requires clarity, understanding, the imagination of the final result, correspondingly, the higher the attitude of the reserved opening, the higher the creativity it is lower, it is difficult to conceive of ideas, to initiate something. The negative relationship is also noted with aggressiveness aggressivity ($r = -0,134, p \leq 0,032$), which means that the creative process cannot exist in aggression, it requires freedom of expression, the favorable psychological climate. We observe a negative correlation with manipulation ($r = -0,185, p \leq 0,003$), which indicates that in the position of distraction, confusion, unclear the subject is not willing to create something.

A negative correlation is found between competitiveness and several attitudinal tendencies: dominant opening ($r = -0,132, p \leq 0,035$), reserve opening ($r = -0,141, p \leq 0,024$), opening ($r = -0,156, p \leq 0,012$), passive submission ($r = -0,145, p \leq 0,020$), aggressive submission ($r = -0,131, p \leq 0,035$), which means that a high level of competitiveness implies a low level of attitudinal tendencies of openness, manifested by empathy, understanding of others; low level whose type of submission, manifested by withdrawal itself, acceptance without discernment of events, situations, passive flight.

At the same time, we find a significant negative relationship between hunger and reserve opening ($r = -0,136, p \leq 0,030$), aggressivity ($r = -0,134, p \leq 0,032$), opening ($r = -0,125, p \leq 0,046$), manipulation ($r = -0,143, p \leq 0,022$), passive submission ($r = -0,132, p \leq 0,034$), active submission ($r = -0,132, p \leq 0,034$), aggressive submission ($r = -0,146, p \leq 0,019$), which may be explained by the fact that maximum highlighting and renown cannot be established in the social environment by manifesting aggressive attitudes, by manipulating with people, by aggressive submission.

The significant negative ratio is established between protection and dominant opening ($r = -0,128, p \leq 0,040$), aggressivity ($r = -0,161, p \leq 0,010$), passive submission ($r = -0,131, p \leq 0,013$), active submission ($r = -0,213, p \leq 0,001$), aggressive submission ($r = -0,168, p \leq 0,007$). Which means that the defense against fear, anxiety or danger cannot be achieved by manifesting an open attitude; a guarantee of the fulfillment of a commitment; anticipation is opposed with aggression, with aggressive submission, active flight.

Conclusions. Therefore, the process of forming values is a whole mechanism, presented by a continuous process, which starts from the externalization of the internalized behaviors, involving the entire psychic sphere of the subject, after forming attitudes and beliefs in which the corresponding value takes shape and is developed perpetually through interactions with others. values. Thus, value orientations encompass the set of attitudes, beliefs, behaviors monitored by a value or a number of values.

Attitude always has a reference object, more or less determined, which can be exposed by the attitude of a person towards the object, person, event, institution, etc. Attitude requires the presence of the reference object of a conceptual or empirical nature, which is based on affective tendencies of pleasure or repulsion, directed towards or against this object.

The shaping of values takes place in the social environment in the favorable psychological climate based on tendencies and attitudinal directives suitable for the proper positioning of the person towards a thing.

Adolescence is a relatively unstable period in the attitudes manifestation, in the appreciation and establishment of the causal relations between the subject and the unfolded ones. The evolution of the attitudinal tendencies is outlined towards youth, which was confirmed by higher indices compared to the indices of the subjects.

Significant negative relationships indicate that values with aggressive attitudes, manipulation, aggressive and active submission are not possible. The formation of values (and not non-values) requires the presence of positive prosocial attitudes and the favorable environment.

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ЦІННІСНІ ОРІЄНТАЦІЇ ТА ВІДНОСИНИ: ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ПРОЯВУ ТА ВЗАЄМОЗВ'ЯЗКУ У ПІДЛІТКОВОМУ ТА МОЛОДІЖНОМУ ВІЦІ

Вивчення ціннісних орієнтацій та поглядів передбачає аналіз наукових підходів і різних теорій у галузі філософії, психології, педагогіки щодо визначень понять: значення, ціннісна орієнтація, установка. Окреслено різні наукові положення щодо інших елементів особистості, структурних компонентів ціннісної орієнтації, процесу їх формування та функціонування.

Мета дослідження: визначити особливості прояву та взаємозв'язку ціннісних орієнтацій та установок у підлітковому та юнацькому віці.

Методологія. Для експериментальної діагностики відносин використовувались такі інструменти: «Ставлення, яке найчастіше приймають» за Фабрісом Лакомбом, та ціннісна орієнтація – методика визначення ціннісних орієнтацій.

Наукова новизна. Отримані дані дозволяють визначити співвідношення відносин та цінностей з точки зору структурного змісту; встановити специфіку прояву та взаємозв'язку між ціннісними відносинами та поглядами зі структурної точки зору їх функціонування, особливості їх проявів та стосунків у сучасних підлітків та юнаків.

Висновки. Дослідження, здійснене з теоретичної та експериментальної перспектив, дозволило: виокремити процес формування цінностей, орієнтований на формування настроїв та зворотне функціонування, прояв поглядів, підпорядкованих системі цінностей особистості; встановити специфіку прояву та співвідношення цінностей та поглядів у сучасних підлітків та юнаків. Злагожене та структуроване формування світогляду шляхом організації та розвитку поведінки, пізнання, афективної сфери, переконань, а отже, ціннісних формувань суб'єкта, що бере участь в освітньому процесі, забезпечить прогресивну еволюцію розвитку особистості починаючи з підліткового та юнацького віку.

Ключові слова: ціннісна орієнтація, цінність, ставлення, юність, молодь.

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